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REGIONAL REPORT ON SOCIAL EXCLUSION AND SOCIAL ECONOMY INITIATIVES IN RURAL AREAS

Bodrogköz – Hungary

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1. Introduction

The main aim of this report was to collect information regarding the situation of rural areas and the communities residing in each of the participating regions in the ESIRA project (ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS HORIZON 101136253). These reports will act as the basis of D4.1, “Benchmark study on social exclusion in rural areas,” and D4.2, “Multi-level analysis of social economy initiatives in rural areas”.

This report aimed to go beyond the literature and statistical data available and, together with the organisations participating in the pilots, explore the regions' situations and the drivers behind the disadvantages.

The report introduces the territorial organization of Hungary and analyses the situation of people living in rural areas, focusing on territorial inequalities.

A deeper examination of the drivers of vulnerability and social exclusion in rural contexts was done in Cigánd Districts. The analysis considers the social processes in the region and the livelihood opportunities at the municipal level. Existing assets and hidden resources in the municipality were assessed according to statistical data and the opinions of the leading local social economy stakeholders.

2. Methodology

The research methodology of this report included **mixed tools**: desk research and literature review for getting to know the local context, statistical data collection, and interviews. We have gathered and reviewed strategic and program-level documents regarding the district; scientific literature; evaluation reports; history of the area; EU programme documents; laws etc.

This literature review was complemented with statistical data from central and territorial statistical databases and from literature.

We have conducted six interviews in the district with colleagues from a charity which is active in the region (and who are the MAP managers), local social economy organisations, and local mayors; and we have complemented the qualitative data with the results of a case study we have conducted in 2023 in the area. This case study was part of a set of research and project evaluation carried out for the Catching-up Settlements programme, which is a national social inclusion programme for the most disadvantaged settlements and people living there. The project methodology of the Catching-up Settlement programme envisaged different data collections techniques, focusing on different aspects (the end beneficiaries, the implementers, the social care system surrounding this programme etc.). For the case study we have interviewed experts from social institutions, EU-funded projects and local administration, for a total of six key informants; the interviews have focused (among the programme-specific questions) on the social exclusion in the district, and the challenges people who are living there face.

There were two challenges hindering the interviews: one was the Hungarian local (and EU Parliament) elections, which were held in early June, and due to which most institutional actors were not as cooperative as they would otherwise be (because this was the period of the election campaigns, and political leaders were even more selective with who they talk to and about what, and more wary of strangers who will ask them about the difficulties in their municipalities; and they would not encourage their colleagues or otherwise adjacent people to give interviews as well). The other one was the fact that the formulation of the MAP in the project has happened alongside with the formulation of the report; but it was not possible to meet the stakeholders jointly. However, the inputs from the initial MAP meetings were incorporated into the report, as we have conducted expert interviews with the MAP managers, who have shared the main impressions and results with us.

3. Country overview: Hungary

3.1 Territorial system of the country

Hungary consists of **8 regions, 19 counties, 197 districts** (23 of these are in the capital); the districts outside of the capital are made up of settlements. Every level covers the whole territory of the country. The lower levels of territorial units fit on the whole into the next, larger level units; they don't extend beyond the area of the larger level.

There is a planning and statistical region level (NUTS-2) between the county and country level. These statistical regions are not administrative units in the classical sense (no self-government or any administrative body), but rather target areas of the European Union's regional politics. At present the territory of the country is divided into **eight planning and statistical regions**, six of these being made up of three counties:

- Western Transdanubia (Győr-Moson-Sopron, Vas, Zala),
- Central Transdanubia, (Komárom-Esztergom, Fejér, Veszprém),
- Northern Hungary (Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén, Heves, Nógrád),
- Northern Great Plain (Hajdú-Bihar, Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok, Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg),
- Southern Great Plain (Bács-Kiskun, Békés, Csongrád),
- Southern Transdanubia (Baranya, Somogy, Tolna).
- Pest county as well as Budapest function as independent regions.

Counties are the oldest territorial administrative levels. Today the county's self-government's competence is basically limited to the administration of their own institutions, management of their own assets and some coordination between the self-governments of the settlements inside the county.

Districts were established in 2013 as the lowest territorial level and organisational units of the public administration, situated between the levels of settlement and county. The strongest role of the districts is administrative. "Government windows" are one-stop-shops for administrative services in Hungary located in the district centre towns. Since 2016, child welfare and family support services have also been the responsibility of the district centre municipalities, which must perform the tasks for the whole district. At the same time, the districts currently have no organising, planning or development role in spatial development, social care or education and health (Koltai – Herczeg – Veress, 2023).

Districts are very different from each other. For example, the number of settlements within a district spreads within broad limits. The Debrecen and Hajdúböszörmény districts have only two settlements, while the Zalaegerszeg one has 84. The most populous district is the Miskolc one, with 235,000 inhabitants – 30 times more people live there than in the least populated Bélapátfalva district. There is not quite as big a difference area-wise: the Kaposvár district (1,591.4 km²) is 15 times larger than the

smallest rural district, Dunakeszi. Among the capital's districts, the VII. one (2.09 km²) is 26 times smaller than the largest, the XVII. district (54.8 km²).

The country's western, south-western as well as the northern, north-eastern districts are made up of many settlements, which are mostly small villages with low population number. The districts of the central part of the country and the Great Plain are made up of fewer settlements, but many of these have larger population number and town rank.

Figure 1. Regions, counties and districts of Hungary

Source: https://www.ksh.hu/regionalatlas_administrative_units

In Hungary the following settlement categories exist at present¹: **municipality, large village², town, town of county rank, capital city**. The elected municipal local government has to fulfil all duties which ensure the basic living conditions of the local population and the possibility of direct utilisation of public services meant to secure these living conditions. Towns of county rank fulfil public services which expand beyond their own limits to the whole county or to a large part of it – these are mostly the county seats as well as those towns with 50 thousand inhabitants or more.

According to the state on 1 May 2022, out of the country's 3,155 settlements 348 are towns (out of these there are one capital and 25 towns of county rank), while 2,807 are village municipalities (out of

¹ Act CLXXXIX of 2011 on Local Governments in Hungary

² The title of large village may be used by those municipal local governments which held the large village title at the time when the Act came into force, furthermore they must have at least 3 thousand inhabitants.

these 127 large villages). One-third of the country's settlements are small villages with less than 500 inhabitants; at the same time, only 3% of the country's population live there. The concentration of the population is significant: seven-tenth of the population lives in towns (two-tenth in the capital).

3.2 Strategies and policies

In 2021, the Hungarian Government adopted the new **National Social Inclusion Strategy 2030** (Magyar Nemzeti Társadalmi Felzárkózási Stratégia 2030, referred hereinafter to as NSIS 2030) that builds on the experience of previous years. The main priorities and intervention directions of the previous strategy (in force between 2014 and 2020) are thus continued by the new strategy. The NSIS 2030 includes seven main areas of intervention: birth and childhood, education (from kindergarten to university), youth affairs, employment, territorial inequalities, settlement development, physical and mental health, health care, Roma identity and enforcement of rights.

The three main horizontal aims of the NSIS 2030 are:

- equal access to public services,
- development of the situation of Roma women, and
- digitalisation.

The Strategy's lines of intervention set out the main tasks, while the three-year action plans describe the programmes and interventions through which the government will contribute to poverty reduction. Therefore, the government adopted the **Action Plan 2021-2024 for the Implementation of the NSIS 2030** and set the tasks of the relevant actors. The responsible minister has to prepare regular reports on the results of the implementation of the strategy – first time in May 2023, then in every two years.

Projects funded by the EU's Structural and investment Funds usually have sectoral or municipality-level focus; but in the previous programming period there were **spatial projects** aiming at beneficiary districts:

- Integrated regional children's programmes (EFOP-1.4.2-16);
- Infinite Opportunities – Pilot programme for the territorial catching-up of the most disadvantaged districts (EFOP-1.5.1-17).

We use the evaluation of Koltai – Herczeg – Veress (2023) to summarize how these worked. The EFOP-1.4.2 Integrated regional children's programmes and the EFOP-1.5.1 Infinite Opportunities projects were based on district-based logic. These projects were implemented by actors with a district coverage area, and the projects had the mandatory task of producing documents and plans regarding the situation in the district (District Childhood Strategy, District Diagnosis, Complex District Development Programme), which in many cases were able to serve the district as a whole by reducing internal inequalities. These documents strengthened district-based thinking, but the extent varies amongst the projects.

The developments were carried out by professional implementers who either worked in primary care themselves (e.g. in the family and child welfare centre) or worked very closely with it. At the same time, staff shortages have meant that projects have often been unable to do more than add new tasks to those already working in the area, so that while capacity has increased in the district, in many cases this has meant that rather than 40, the same professional has been working 60-80 hours a week on different projects. Even so in some cases, the Infinite Opportunities programmes were also able to complement the local service palette, especially where they were able to provide services that neither basic services nor the other projects could (e.g. debt management, community programmes, labour market programmes).

However, it should be stressed that, as these improvements were carried out in the context of projects of finite duration (with limited activity during the maintenance period) and since their continuation is doubtful, in most cases there is no prospect of a lasting reduction in the capacity deficit. Some of the projects transitioned to the FETE programme (see below), which eased the issue of maintenance and continuity, but they lost their district-based focus.

In 2019, the Hungarian government launched an independent programme, the **Catching-up Settlements programme** (Felzárkózó települések program, FETE), for the social inclusion of disadvantaged settlements and people living there. The aim of this comprehensive programme is to reach the 300 most disadvantaged settlements, with a focus on children and youth. The focus is on the settlement level, and any greater territorial cooperation is not part of the program.

Charities and NGOs are the main implementers of the programme. The main coordinator is the Hungarian Charity Service of the Order of Malta. As shown in Table 1, in recent years the number of settlements included in the programme has progressively increased.

Table 1 Number of settlements in the Catching-up Settlements programme

Year	Number of additional settlements
2019	31
2020	36
2021-2022	51
2023	60

Source: fete.hu

A variety of measures is used depending on local conditions: social assistance, early childhood development and health care services, education and training activities, work socialisation and skills development, housing interventions/measures, crime prevention, reduction of drug use, victim assistance, and necessary infrastructural investments. From 2023, the programme basically relies on European Union funds, mostly Hungary’s Recovery and Resilience Plan.

Most often, it is the local municipalities that are responsible for providing and ensuring equal opportunities and inclusion in Hungary. To accomplish this duty, since 1 July 2013, municipalities can only receive support from state funds, European Union subsidies or other funds provided by

international agreements if they have a **Local Equal Opportunity Programme** (Helyi Esélyegyenlőségi Program, referred hereinafter to as HEP)³.

The municipalities have to prepare this Programme document every 5 years and review it every 2 years. Specific target groups of the programme are disadvantaged children, Roma people, those living in poverty, the elderly, people with disability and women. The HEP are based on:

- action plans related to the problems of disadvantaged groups and
- analyses of social, educational, employment, health and housing issues and situations.

The action plans have to solve real problems, and they are implemented based on priority order and with a deadline and have a dedicated person who is responsible for the implementation.

To help local municipalities in creating effective and lawful HEP, the Directorate-General for Creating Social Opportunities (Társadalmi Esélyteremtési Főigazgatóság) offers advisory and compliance service through its network of equal opportunity mentors. There are local consultation forums where the local municipalities and the involved partners cooperate to solve the problems and create the related action plans.

Nevertheless, in most cases the settlements just fulfil their obligation to write these HEP and these are not the documents that lead their actions.

3.3 Territorial inequalities in Hungary

The Hungarian spatial structure shows **large territorial inequalities**: next to the more developed capital in the western and northwestern parts of Hungary, there are less developed southern and eastern regions.

By using a complex indicator measuring the districts socio-economic status, Hungarian districts were divided into four categories:

- Non-beneficiary districts,
- Beneficiary districts,
- Districts to be developed,
- Districts to be developed with a complex programme.⁴

Out of the 197 districts, the best performing 88 got into the “non-beneficiary” category; 55 were named “beneficiary”; 18 were classified as “districts to be developed”, and the ones in the worst condition were put in the category to be “developed with a complex programme”. The spatial distribution of the different categories can be seen in the map below (Fig. 2). 10% of the country’s population lives in districts to be developed with a complex programme. In these districts the urban-

³ *Equal Opportunity Programme must comply with the regulations in the Act of CXXV of 2003.*

⁴ *Government Decree 290/2014 (XI. 26.) on the classification of beneficiary districts*

rural differences continue to grow: there are few jobs and many families move away; at the same time, people with low education or part of the Roma population are usually unable to move to towns/regions with better economic prospects.

Figure 2. Beneficiary districts in Hungary

Source: https://www.ksh.hu/docs/teruletiatlasz/beneficiary_districts.pdf

The territorial concentration of poverty is typical: in the most disadvantaged settlements, one can find the combination of severe unemployment, social and health related problems, poor housing conditions, low-quality human and public services and insufficient availability of utilities and public transportation. There is a lack of professionals – both in terms of numbers and modern, up-to-date knowledge – and local communities are weak. Most of these settlements do not have a functioning economy, working businesses, or job opportunities outside public employers as employability is a fundamental problem. So, the depopulation of these territories continues along with the changing of the ratio of Roma and non-Roma inhabitants.

The indicators calculated based on the EU-SILC can only be interpreted at the regional level in case of Hungary due to the sample sizes used in the data collection. To be able to go deeper we present the results of Tátrai (2022), who calculated the indicators of income poverty and severe material deprivation in Hungary using small-area estimation methods at the district level. For this estimation, Tátrai (2022) looked for demographic, labour market and economic variables that are available at the district level and are closely related to poverty metrics. Thus, the method estimates higher poverty rates for districts with a higher proportion of high-risk population.

Based on these results of Tátrai (2022), we can present the proportions of **people living in severe material deprivation** from 2014 at district level (see Figure 3). In this year, on average, 24% of the population of the country was living in severe material deprivation; district averages scattered between 8 and 56%. The proportion of the deprived population was particularly high in the northern part of Borsod and the eastern districts of Szatmár, Jászapáti and Hegyhát districts. The proportion of the poor is below average in Northern Transdanubia and in the capital and its northern agglomeration.

Figure 3. Proportion of people living in severe material deprivation on district level (percentage) – 2014

Source of data: Tátrai (2022)

The territorial break-down of the **at-risk-of poverty** measure shows a similar pattern than in the case of severe material deprivation (see Figure 4). While the at-risk-of-poverty rate was 15 percent nationally in 2014, the districts' rates ranged between 2 and 44%. The districts in the worst situation are located in the same place as in the previous aspects: in the southern part of Transdanubia and in northeastern part of Hungary. In the interior of the country, the districts of Törökszentmiklós, Heves and Kunhegyes have a high proportion of people living below the poverty threshold.

Figure 4. Proportion of people at-risk-of-poverty on district level (percentage) – 2014

Source of data: Tátrai (2022)

3.4 The situation of Roma people in Hungary

The biggest minority ethnic group in Hungary is the **Roma**. According to the 2022 census, 2.5% of respondents, or **210,000 people**, have categorised themselves as belonging to the Roma community. However, it must be mentioned that both self-reported surveys and external categorisation are limited: the former usually undercounts the population of Roma people due to respondent's reluctance, while the latter methodology implies greater potential for bias and contingencies (Lajtai, 2020). In the previous census in 2011, 316,000 people declared themselves as Roma, while a 2010-13 expert survey found 876,000 Roma living in Hungary (Pénzes et al., 2018).

According to the FRA (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights) Roma survey (conducted in 2021), in Hungary **77% of Roma people are at risk of poverty** (compared to the 12% of the general population) (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2023). This is a very high number, and risk of poverty is in many cases paired with spatial segregation as well. This means that while Roma people live in every part of the country, they live in higher proportions in disadvantaged districts; and in bigger and/or wealthier towns they are more likely to live in a segregated area.

According to the Hungarian National Social Inclusion Strategy 2030 (MNTFS, 2021), there has been a vast improvement at the national level in the general employment situation since 2009, which has meant that the share of unemployed in the active population had fallen significantly. However, this improvement did not reach all groups of population evenly: those in a vulnerable situation or marginalised groups (such as Roma people), are still in worse situation in the labour market.

According to the Strategy, there are, among others, two crucial factors in the labour market which can affect one's employability: educational attainment and ethnicity. This means that those with a lower education, and those who (are perceived to) belong to a stigmatised ethnic group (in Hungary, this means Roma), have more hardship finding good jobs.

The Strategy shows that while the country-level employment has grown to 70% in 2020, in 2019, only 45.5% of Roma people (of whom 16% were in public employment) and 39.4% of those with a maximum of 8 grades were employed. Also, while there is an undeniable convergence between the employment rates of Roma and non-Roma people, public work is (or more precisely, was) one of the main drivers of this process. However, there are studies which have shown that public work, apart from giving a very low level of income, usually is not a gate to the primary labour market but rather has other functions in the life of the municipalities and the people working in them (Koltai et. al, 2018b; Gerő – Vígvári, 2019; Lipták, 2020). Thus, while the share of public work has been on the decline in recent years, this still has a contradictory effect on the employment of Roma people as a whole.

The same overall increase with big differences and disadvantage to Roma people is true to educational attainment as well. According to census data, in the overall population, the share of people over 15 who have only primary level education has been decreased by 9 percentage points in ten years (from the 2011 32% to 23% in 2022). Among those who identified themselves as Roma, there were an even bigger decrease in the share of undereducation – but from a much higher basis: there was a 14 percentage points decrease, from the 2011 81% to the 2022 67% (which is almost three times the

percentage of the overall population). The share of Roma people with a higher education certification is very low (3% among those over 15).

3.5 Social economy

The history of the social economy in Hungary goes back to the **19th century**. At that time, cooperatives, NGOs and other enterprises whose primary objective was not profit existed already. During the **communist period**, these organisations went through a radical transformation, as they fell under state control and basically ceased to be autonomous. The cooperatives were primarily agricultural and were large-scale state-owned socialist farms. Nevertheless, they received new impetus after the regime change. Around the time of the **regime change**, new legislation was introduced to allow for the creation of various forms of non-profit organisations (mainly foundations and associations); although, these were typically charitable organisations. The concept of social economy and social enterprise has entered the country in the **1990s**, mainly through the work of the international development organisations. Act XXXVIII of 1992 (hereinafter: Áht.) enabled ministries and local municipalities to become founders or owners, at their own discretion, of economic organisations and non-profit organisations (for example public benefit companies and public foundations). Since 2006 (Act X of 2006 on cooperatives), it has been possible to set up non-profit companies and the social cooperative form has been established.

Since the 2000s, the social dimension of cooperatives has garnered increasing importance, as well as the need for developing the social economy sector (Petheő et al., 2010). In 2006, legislative measures were initiated to regulate the form of social cooperatives for the first time in Hungary. Act X of 2006 on cooperatives defined the term as follows: “A cooperative is an organisation with legal personality, founded with a share capital of a certain amount, operating according to the principles of open membership and variable capital, with the aim of promoting the satisfaction of the economic and other social (cultural, educational, social, health) needs of its members” (Cooperatives Act/Szövetkezeti törvény, 2006) The law also defines the concept of a social cooperative, which is defined as an entity that exists for the purpose of creating working conditions for its disadvantaged members and otherwise promoting the improvement of their social situation. In 2016, an amendment to the law stipulated that social cooperatives must have at least one member of the local or national government in addition to natural persons, with the aim of preventing abuse. The 2019 amendment to the law created what are known as start-up social cooperatives.

In Hungary, **non-governmental organisations** (NGOs) play a crucial role in civil society, contributing to various social, cultural and humanitarian activities. The legal framework for NGOs in Hungary is mainly based on the Civil Code and the Act on the Freedom of Association, the Public Benefit Status and the Operation and Financing of Civil Society Organisations (Act CLXXV of 2011). The main forms of NGOs are **associations and foundations**. Associations (Egyesület) are usually formed for the mutual benefit of their members and can pursue a wide range of activities, including cultural, educational, environmental and social causes. Associations must be registered with the court to obtain legal

personality. Foundations (Alapítvány) are established to achieve a specific public interest objective, such as education, health or environmental protection. They do not have members.

NGOs and social economy organizations in Hungary can apply for a special status called **Public Benefit Organisations** (Közhasznú Szervezetek)⁵. These are NGOs that carry out activities that benefit the public or the wider community, such as health care, social services or education. To be recognised as a public benefit organisation, the NGO must apply for this status and meet certain criteria, such as having transparent operations and providing services that are widely accessible. Charities are eligible for tax breaks and other forms of government support.

In Hungary, the social economy also includes enterprises established as a business company. Since 2007, a **non-profit business company** can be established. These companies were previously governed by Act IV of 2006 on Companies (Gt.), which has now been repealed, and are now governed by Act V of 2013 (Ptk.) and Section 9/F of Act V of 2006 on Company Registration, Court Proceedings and Winding-up (Ctv.).

A non-profit-making company is a company with a specific function which does not aim to generate income for its members. It may engage in commercial activities only as an ancillary activity. The profits of the company may not be distributed among its members. The company must be formed with the assistance of a lawyer and registered with the competent Companies Court. A non-profit business corporation may also apply for public benefit status if it meets the requirements. A non-profit company can be established in any form of company (non-profit public limited company, non-profit limited liability company, non-profit limited liability partnership).

A **social cooperative** is a "community enterprise" organised on a voluntary basis, based on the primacy of the community interest, with the aim of creating work opportunities for its disadvantaged members and otherwise contributing to the improvement of their social situation. Cooperatives are usually set up on the basis of a grassroots initiative, but in Hungary they are more connected to the local authority, as from 2016 a local or minority authority or charity organization must be among the members. Start Social Cooperatives, which are based on public employment, are characterised by their main activities being agricultural production, food processing, production of local products and services. In 2006, legislative measures were initiated to regulate the form of social cooperatives for the first time in Hungary. Act X of 2006 on cooperatives defined the term as follows: "A cooperative is an organisation with legal personality, founded with a share capital of a certain amount, operating according to the principles of open membership and variable capital, with the aim of promoting the satisfaction of the economic and other social (cultural, educational, social, health) needs of its members" (Cooperatives Act/Szövetkezeti törvény, 2006) The law also defines the concept of a social cooperative, which is defined as an entity that exists for the purpose of creating working conditions for its disadvantaged members and otherwise promoting the improvement of their social situation. In 2016, an amendment to the law stipulated that social cooperatives must have at least one member of the local or national

⁵ The Public Benefit status has been established by the Public Benefit Organisations Act (156/1997)

government in addition to natural persons, with the aim of preventing abuse. The 2019 amendment to the law created what are known as start-up social cooperatives.

These latter forms of non-profit enterprises are not included in the national NGO statistical system due to their operational and regulatory specificities.

In Hungary, there is **no framework legislation on social enterprises and the solidarity economy**⁶, but there are several pieces of legislation covering the social economy more broadly, such as on NGOs, voluntary activities in the public interest, cooperatives and social cooperatives.⁷ There is no specifically designated government body or institution either: different ministries cover specific aspects of the sector. Ministry of National Economy coordinates EU co-funded programs to support social enterprises, while Ministry of Interior has a Social Cooperatives Coordination Department; other ministries may also engage.

Based on the data of the Hungarian Central Statistical Office (KSH), in 2022 there were **60,878 non-profit organisations** operating in Hungary. The importance of the non-profit sector in the national economy, in terms of average revenue to GDP and number of employees, was 4.7%. In 2022, the real value of total revenue of non-profit organisations increased by 17% compared to the previous year, and the number of employees also increased by 3.3%. The weight of the nonprofit sector in the economy increased steadily between 2015 and 2022, based on the average of revenue as a share of GDP and the average of the share of employees.

Almost one third of the almost 61,000 non-profit organizations (19,196) were foundations, while two thirds (41,682) were associations (e.g. clubs). The main activities of foundations were education (31%), social welfare (16%) and culture (16%), while the main activities of associations were leisure (21%), sports (22%) and culture (17%). As a result of legislative changes, the share of organisations with public benefit status decreased in 2015 and was 22% in 2022. The share of organisations with an annual income of less than HUF 500,000 (around EUR 1,300) remains high, reaching 32% in 2022. The increase in the total income of the non-profit sector is mainly due to the increase in the income of public and trust foundations and organisations active in the field of community development (source of data: Hungarian Central Statistical Office (KSH)).

Hungary does not have a strategy for the development of NGOs or the social economy. NGOs (especially those with public benefit status) are supported by numerous programmes and benefits. For example, the National Cooperation Fund – a central budget allocation that supports the functioning of civil society organisations, national cohesion and the promotion of the common good, as well as the professional activities of civil society organisations. In addition, public-benefit NGOs benefit from a

⁶ Please note that solidarity economy is a very rarely used term in Hungary, either in policy or in regulation. And as it has been indicated earlier, there is no single legal or strategic equivalent for any of the terms of social economy, solidarity economy, social and solidarity economy. Therefore, their content and framework are at times confusing.

⁷ Fundamental Law of Hungary, Act CLXXV of 2011 on the Right of Association, the Public Benefit Status and the Functioning and Support of Non-Governmental Organisations (Civil Act), Act CLXXXI of 2011 on the Judicial Registration of NGOs and the Procedural Rules Related thereto (Cnytv.), Act V of 2013 (Civil Code), Act LXXXVIII of 2005 on voluntary activities in the public interest, Government Decree No 350/2011 (XII. 30.) on certain aspects of the management, fundraising and public benefit of non-governmental organisations, Act X of 2006 on cooperatives,

number of tax advantages. Citizens can also donate 1% of their income tax to a registered NGO of their choice.

The deficiencies in Hungary's civil society are attributed to its relatively short history, limited organizational development, and dependency on the public sector for funding and support. This reliance hampers NGOs' ability to engage in independent advocacy and community organizing. Similar challenges exist in other post-socialist countries, but Hungary's situation is exacerbated by its political shift towards illiberal democracy since 2010. This shift has further marginalized civil society, limiting its potential to contribute to social and economic growth (Szalai-Svensson, 2019).

3.6 Social enterprises in Hungary

In Hungary there is **no uniform definition or legal framework for social enterprises**. Several definitions used by EU funding sources and professional support organisations, as well as by national and EU institutions and organisations involved in research in the sector, are present in both public discourse and practice. Among the concepts related to social entrepreneurship, the social economy and social enterprise concepts are increasingly coming to the forefront of Hungarian policy interest (G. Fekete-Hubai-Kiss-Mihály 2018, European Commission 2019, HÉTFA 2021). In 2016, a **strategic working group** was established under the leadership of the National Employment Public Benefit Non-profit Ltd. (OFA), with the aim of creating a single label. According to the working group, "social enterprises are mission-driven organisations: they aim to solve a social problem through business activities, in many cases using innovative ideas. Their financial sustainability is achieved to a significant extent through the provision and sale of socially responsible and marketable products and services" (OFA, 2017b: 3).

Since the 2010s, numerous **national and EU funds** have supported the creation and development of social enterprises, thus orienting the conceptual definition of these organisations. In the national policy discourse, support for social enterprises was limited to social cooperatives in the period 2007-13 but has been extended since 2014⁸. The measures targeting social enterprises in the 2014-20 period within the Economic Development and Innovation Operational Programme (GINOP), adapt the definition of social enterprises as set out in the European Commission's Communication "Social Business Initiative" (2011). The Operational Program defines the primary target group as "non-profit and civil society organisations and social co-operatives which, in addition to their social objectives, have business objectives, feed the results of their management back into the social purpose argument and apply the principle of participatory decision-making in their budgets and organisational functioning" (GINOP call 5.1.2).

A study by G. Fekete (2018) classified social enterprises in Hungary into six distinct groups, taking into account their legal form, sectoral linkages, and typical social goals and areas of activity:

⁸ In the period 2014-20, social economy has been given a higher political priority and more resources have been allocated to it. This was partly due to EU policy developments and partly to the expansion of public work scheme. Hungarian policy saw a good opportunity for social enterprises run by local authorities to create jobs for those in public employment.

1. **Public service social enterprises**, which typically perform municipal or public functions, mostly in the social and utility sectors. These organisations receive public subsidies but also have market revenues. They are most often organised as foundations, not-for-profit companies or social cooperatives. Public service social enterprises are often closely linked to the public sector and therefore have a lower degree of autonomy.
2. **Entrepreneurial NGOs** are those classic NGOs, mostly in the form of foundations or associations, which supplement their income from public funds or donations with market revenues in order to achieve their social or environmental objectives. Due to the complementary nature of their economic activities, they are characterised by their non-profit character.
3. **Labour market integration organizations**, which are a specific group of social enterprises (WISE – work integration social enterprises) with a social purpose. The activities of this type of organisations are aimed at the direct employment of various disadvantaged target groups in order to mobilise/integrate them into the labour market or to help them supplement their income and strengthen their self-sufficiency (e.g. gardening, sewing courses). Given the disadvantages of the target group in the labour market, these organisations are highly dependent on external funding.
4. **Community enterprises for local development** have tried to replace the local community and economic functions of the agricultural cooperatives that disappeared after the regime change. These types of organisations are committed to their aim of improving the vitality of the community and the wellbeing of local residents, with the form of organisation changing dynamically in response to the funding environment. Their main activity is usually the production of agricultural products, or the provision of services related to the operation and development of the community. They usually have close links with the local government.
5. The two most important characteristics of **social start-ups** are their profitable economic activity and their social responsibility objective.
6. Social economy initiatives of **smaller group of individual social entrepreneurs**. Reciprocity, participation and democratic decision-making are the dominant principles in their operation. Social and Solidarity Economy organizations are characterised by the fact that their activities go beyond the market economy.

In presenting the social economy and social enterprises in Hungary, we cannot ignore the public work scheme, which has a major impact on the operation of social enterprises in Hungary. The employment policy instruments outlined in the **Hungarian Work Plan in 2011** define, among other things, the relationship between public work and the social economy. According to the strategy, the social economy is a kind of **transition between public work and the open labour market**, with social cooperatives being the next stage of employment for people; providing work experience to those leaving public employment and become cooperative members or employees. Public employment and social enterprise differ in their financing and organisation, with the activities and management of social

enterprise being closer to the open labour market and competitive market actors. Therefore, since 2013, the Government has been supporting the development and operation of social cooperatives related to public work programmes. One of the forms of this was the model programme called **Start Work** launched in 2011. Then, in 2013, an amendment to the law on cooperatives allowed municipalities to become members of social cooperatives. As a result, the National Employment Public Benefit Non-profit Ltd. (OFA) launched a support program entitled "Focus on support for social cooperatives organised on the basis of public employment with municipal membership" (Koltai, 2018a; Koltai, 2018b). 199 social cooperatives received support from the nationally funded programme (currently running) between 2016 and 2023, which resulted in the creation of jobs for nearly 1,400 disadvantaged workers. The beneficiary social cooperatives had employed an average of 7 workers (Belügyminisztérium, 2020).

The social co-operatives based on public work were mainly funded by municipalities previously in the Start Work model programme. The main local partners of these social cooperatives are the municipalities, who play a key role in managing the liquidity problems and administrative tasks arising in the operation of the organisations and enable the implementation of local development in a complex system. In 2019, the Law on Cooperatives had been amended to include the concept of a **Start Work social cooperative**, a social cooperative that (in addition to the provisions on social cooperatives) is established and operated by a municipality that is a public employer and whose founders include a person who is employed by the municipality as a public employee. Since 2014, the number of social cooperatives based on public employment has been growing rapidly, but since 2017 this trend has slowed down. Currently, there are 183 Start social cooperatives based on public employment in the country. The main activities of social cooperatives based on public employment are typically services, food processing, industry and sales. Most of them are located in disadvantaged settlements in Csongrád, Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén, Baranya and Hajdú-Bihar counties (Belügyminisztérium, 2020).

Social enterprises in Hungary can take many legal forms. Social enterprises can choose between non-profit, business and NGO legal forms; the latter can only carry out economic activities if this is not their core activity. The most common legal forms of social enterprises are **non-profit companies, civil organisations** (associations, foundations) that (partly) market their activities, and **social cooperatives**. The influence of the supporting environment can be seen in the fact that the most common legal forms in Hungary are those that have been recognised as beneficiaries of support measures since the EU-accession. The social cooperative form was introduced in 2006, and municipalities have been able to become members of these cooperatives since 2013, with membership becoming mandatory in 2016. Several experts and advocacy organisations have criticised this decision, arguing that it could create an asymmetric power situation and thus limit the principle of cooperativism (Edmiston et al., 2016; National Association of Social Cooperatives, 2017).

Several empirical studies have attempted to quantify the number of social enterprises due to the absence of a single policy definition. These studies provide an approximate picture of the sector's size. Expert estimates can provide a good measure of the identification of social enterprises from an economic perspective in Hungary. Based on the 2015 central statistical office data of the baseline study

on social economy, there were **13,014 organizations identified as social enterprises** in Hungary. The study defined the population as foundations, associations, church organizations, and non-profit economic associations with an annual turnover of at least HUF 500,000 and at least one employee, as well as all social cooperatives (G. Fekete et al., 2017). In terms of the economic weight of social enterprises, the total turnover of organisations, excluding social cooperatives, reached HUF 753,686 million in 2016, and their annual turnover was equivalent to 2.1% of GDP (Kiss-Mihály, 2019).

HÉTFA Research Institute has a database of balance sheet data of Hungarian enterprises, which includes information on non-profit business organisations and social cooperatives, but only limited information on foundations and associations. For each of these legal forms, we only have information on those organisations that have submitted their balance sheets in due time, so the database is incomplete. In 2022, the database contained data on 871 social cooperatives, 3,555 non-profit economic organisations and 43,187 NGOs. Only 2% of the NGOs met the criterion of having an enterprise income of HUF 500,000. The average annual revenue of social cooperatives in 2022 was HUF 57 million, while that of non-profit enterprises was HUF 212 million. The average number of employees was 3 in the case of social cooperatives, 31 in the case of non-profit enterprises and 1 in the case of NGOs. 75% of the income of social cooperatives and 53% of the income of non-profit enterprises came from turnover, in addition to various national and EU subsidies, tasking income and donations.

Table 2. Some economic data of SSE organisations by legal status in 2022 (thousands HUF and EUR)

	thousand HUF	EUR
Personnel expenses (average)		
Social cooperatives	25,205	64,628
Non-profit enterprises	152,897	392,044
Per capita personnel costs (average)		-
Social cooperatives	16,995	43,577
Non-profit enterprises	5,799	14,869
Material expenditure (average)		-
Social cooperatives	30,414	77,985
Non-profit enterprises	282,952	725,518
Tax liability (average)		-
Social cooperatives	250	641
Non-profit enterprises	1,247	3,197
Assets (average)		-
Social cooperatives	35,471	90,951
Non-profit enterprises	2,614,193	6,703,059
Associations, foundations	26,044	66,779
Profit after tax (average)		-
Social cooperatives	1,785	4,577
Non-profit enterprises	50	128
Profit from core activities of associations, foundations	769	1,972
Profit from business activities of associations, foundations	65	167

Total income (average)		-
Social cooperatives	64,304	164,882
Non-profit enterprises	638,642	1,637,544
Total income of associations, foundations	695	1,782
Income per employee (average)		-
Social cooperatives	28,489	73,049
Non-profit enterprises	12,612	32,338
Share of market income in total income (average)		
Social cooperatives	75.05%	
Non-profit enterprises	53.27%	

Source: HÉTFA calculation based on the annual balance sheet database of farmers' organisations

Hungarian social enterprises are very diverse in their activities. They are most active in the following areas: employment, education, social care, culture, leisure, hobbies, community development, economic development, environmental protection, sport, health and international relations (G. Fekete et al., 2017).

Table 3. Main activity of SSE organizations by ILO sectors in 2022 (thousands HUF)

	Social cooperatives	Non-profit enterprise organisations		Foundations/ Association	%
A Agriculture, forestry, fishing	78	55	3%	821	2%
C Manufacturing	173	85	6%	16	0%
D Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	0	24	1%	0	0%
E Water supply	10	134	3%	10	0%
F Construction	91	76	4%	4	0%
G Trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	110	60	4%	21	0%
H Transport, storage	7	18	1%	10	0%
I Accommodation and food service activities	71	93	4%	41	0%
J Information and communication	10	144	3%	118	0%
K Financial and insurance activities	2	14	0%	13	0%
L Real estate activities	11	104	3%	35	0%
M Professional, scientific and technical activities	54	533	13%	645	2%
N Administrative and support service activities	109	290	9%	236	1%
O Public administration, defence and compulsory social security	2	33	1%	749	2%
P Education	18	429	10%	1,866	4%
Q Human health and social work activities	19	579	14%	1,181	3%
R Arts, entertainment and recreation	27	593	14%	10,360	24%
S Other service activities	78	290	8%	26,680	62%
T Activities of households as employers	1	0	0%	0	0%
U Non-territorial organisation	0	0	0%	11	0%
Total	871	3,554	100%	42,817	100%

Source: HÉTFA calculation based on the annual balance sheet database of farmers' organisations

3.6.1 Strategic framework

In Hungary, there is **no national strategy or framework to support social enterprises**. The social economy area is the second pillar of the employment support system outlined in the 2011 Hungarian Labour Plan, which is an intermediate sector that builds on local opportunities to organise employment for disadvantaged people, partly with public support and partly with own income.

There have been numerous support programmes, some funded by the European Union and others by national funds. The 2006 adoption of Act on cooperatives and subsequent support programmes for the creation of social cooperatives laid the foundations for further support programmes. In the 2000s a dedicated resource of HUF 945 million⁹ was allocated for the development of social cooperatives through the **National Employment Non-profit Ltd (OFA) grant scheme**. The 'Co-operate' tender helped 36 social cooperatives overcome initial difficulties and start sustainable operations. The OFA grant programme has quickly laid the foundations for promoting social cooperatives in Hungary. The programme has been well-received by leaders of NGOs, local authorities, small businesses, and some unemployed individuals.

In 2010, the **New Széchenyi Plan's funding schemes** provided HUF 2.25 billion¹⁰ in development funds to 57 social cooperatives. The aim was to support atypical forms of employment and help disadvantaged members and workers find work. During this period, support was only available to social cooperatives, which contributed to the strengthening and expansion of this legal form. The projects had a strong focus on employment, with beneficiaries emphasizing the long-term impact on employment and the labour market. The focus of many beneficiary organisations was on stabilising the social enterprise and strengthening its business opportunities and did not aim to move participants towards the open labour market. Their employment goals were geared towards the long-term retention of workers (Koltai, 2018a).

During the 2014-20 period, two funding schemes (GINOP-5.1.3-16 and GINOP-5.1.7-17) became available for social enterprises under the **Economic Development and Innovation Operational Programme (GINOP)**, with one opening a year after the other. The funding was open to social cooperatives, church organisations, associations, foundations, and non-profit companies, covering the majority of Hungarian social enterprises. As a result, the focus has shifted from promoting the establishment of new enterprises to enhancing the sustainability and competitiveness of existing social enterprises. Additionally, a pre-qualification procedure has been implemented to serve as a screening process. A total of 528 projects received funding under the GINOP schemes, with some organisations receiving multiple grants. A total of 3,786 jobs were planned to be created under the two schemes, with a total of HUF 24.3 billion¹¹ in fund. Additionally, in Hungary, an interest-free loan scheme (GINOP-

⁹ Approx. 2,4 million euro.

¹⁰ Approx. 5,5 million euro.

¹¹ Approx. 61 million euro.

8.8.1) was launched during the 2014-20 programming period for newly created micro-enterprises and social enterprises by unemployed and inactive persons, with very low take-up¹². Furthermore, the calls for proposals of the Operational Programme for the Development of Human Resources (EFOP-1.11.1)¹³ included a scheme aimed at supporting the development of business and public partnerships between social economy organisations for the integration of people who have been excluded from the labour market (HÉTFA, 2021).

The Hungarian support schemes were characterised by the availability of different types of support with different conditions and scope. However, most of them were project-based, i.e. not available on a permanent basis. The structure of support is unpredictable, and successive supports do not build on each other. Although grants are widely accepted by organisations, as they have been the main source of support for social enterprises over the last decade, they are also a form of path dependency, since writing and managing applications takes a lot of energy and financial resources away from an organisation's business or social activities (HÉTFA 2021).

According to the research of Éva G. Fekete et al. (2017), the three most frequently formulated goals of social enterprises in Hungary are:

- improving the labour market situation,
- achieving goals linked to the municipality and the local community,
- improving the situation of people with disabilities.

3.6.2 The impact of social enterprises on the rural economy

The social economy organizations have impacts on the local economy and society in several areas, which are summarised based on previous research by HÉTFA Research Institute (HÉTFA 2021, Koltai et al. 2018a, Koltai et al. 2018b, Koltai 2019).

On the one hand, social enterprises have a **wide range of economic impacts**, such as

- Economic value added: social enterprises create new value through their activities, producing goods and services that contribute to total local output.
- New innovative products and services: these, typically small enterprises, have a greater potential for innovation, can identify marginal local needs and market niches and serve them in a customised and tailored way.
- In many cases, rural social enterprises build on and make efficient use of local products and crops.

¹² Foglalkoztatás ösztönzése célú Hitelprogram (GINOP-8.8.1-17) – Employment Incentive Loan Programme

¹³ „Kísérleti programok a szociális gazdaság erősítése és a leghátrányosabb helyzetű csoportok elhelyezkedése érdekében non-profit szervezetek és vállalkozások együttműködése révén” (EFOP-1.11.1-17) – "Pilot programmes to strengthen the social economy and the integration of the most disadvantaged groups through cooperation between non-profit organisations and businesses"

- Developing the local economy and supply chains: Social enterprises have developed a wide range of market relationships with local economic actors and communities. Social enterprises active in the processing of raw materials create an important market for local small producers. In some cases, the activities of the social enterprise have had a spill-over effect on the life of the whole community or even the whole sub-region.
- Social enterprises and organisations clearly have an important role to play in increasing the range of available local products: many of them produce innovative, unique products.
- Social enterprises can also have an impact on local economic trends, equilibrium prices and supply chains. Like any other new business, their production activities may encroach on the market of existing businesses. However, very few examples of this have been found.

Social economy in rural areas have a moderate share of direct employment, but in some areas have **achieved particularly good results in helping the reintegration of working-age people excluded from the labour market.**

- Job creation: Although the overall employment weight of social enterprises is not very significant, they create a larger share of additional jobs in municipalities where the number of jobs was very low. Many social enterprises (especially social cooperatives) were created in the context of EU funds and public work with the aim of increasing employment. Many social enterprises were set up in the most disadvantaged districts, so that jobs could be created in the municipalities where they were most needed.
- In many cases, these jobs give disadvantaged or public sector workers the opportunity to work locally in conditions closer to the market.
- In many cases, social enterprises have also indirectly created new jobs.
- The integration of vulnerable groups into the labour market is a key objective of many social enterprises. They provide transitional or permanent employment opportunities for disadvantaged groups (disabled people, women with young children, long-term unemployed).
- Developing (work) socialisation to support labour market integration: in many cases these enterprises have a direct objective of facilitating labour market integration, and in many cases, they contribute significantly to the development of workers' labour market skills through the training and services they provide to their employees.
- Development and training of local human resources: many social enterprises provide training and services not only to their employees but also to others, helping them to improve their position in the labour market and thus increasing the skills of the local workforce.
- Retention: as with all forms of subsidised employment, social enterprises may prove to be more tolerant and attractive places to work than market jobs in the area, making jobseekers more likely to choose and stay in them.

- Labour-draining effect: Social enterprises also need productive labour, so in a demand labour market, if they can offer better conditions, they can suck labour away from other enterprises.
- However, the beneficiaries of their labour market promotion activities are often the local enterprises, which are happy to take on workers 'socialised for work' in promotion programmes.
- A significant number of Hungarian social enterprises have very strong links with public work scheme. There are also many organisations that run a municipal agricultural Start Work pilot programme and sell the products produced in the framework of public work. These organisations produce high value-added products, often based on local traditions, which play an important role in identity building.
- A significant proportion of the public employees working in such social enterprises are unable to find a job in the open labour market due to their living situation or for health reasons and would probably only be able to do so with long and complex support. For them, a social enterprise can be a way forward, but also a more stable, long-term job.

Social enterprises also play an important role in **local community and social development**. This is especially true for small rural communities.

- Improving access to certain services: social enterprises often provide services (including for the needy and elderly) that are not available locally at affordable prices. This is especially important in peripheral areas.
- Strengthening local entrepreneurship and local economic governance: Many social enterprises have strong links with the local community and municipality. Their success can therefore increase the entrepreneurial spirit, experience and influence of the community in economic processes.
- Strengthening spatial development: social enterprises often carry out development that is integrated into the local spatial development system, thus facilitating synergies.
- Impact on social cohesion and local values: Many social enterprises are community-led, such as cooperatives, giving community members a voice and involvement.
- The production of local products helps to preserve local values, often creating a range of products that reinforce local identity, bringing economic benefits and strengthening community cohesion.
- In many cases, the activities of social enterprises provide a model for their surroundings: they can lead to the establishment of their own production, but they can also give meaning to the cultivation of abandoned backyard gardens, providing opportunities for small farms in the area and for households with land to generate income.
- The availability of locally produced, good quality, healthy food, whether primary or processed, without preservatives or additives, is a clear positive outcome.

- The majority of social enterprises place emphasis on developing a distinctive image and local 'brand' for their products and services.
- Through their activities, social enterprises contribute to the development of a network of contacts for disadvantaged target groups. Workplace contacts enrich the network of contacts, mainly of the disadvantaged target group, but also create opportunities for contacts with groups of higher social status.

4. Regional overview: Cigánd region

4.1 Geographic and historical aspects

The **Cigánd district** is located in Hungary, in the North Great Plain region, in Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén country. It is situated in an extremely isolated location, directly next to the Slovak border, surrounded by three rivers: Tisza, Latorca, and Bodrog. It is **one of the most disadvantaged areas in the country**, lacking urban centers. In 2014, the government reorganized the districts in Hungary, leading to the creation of the Cigánd district with 15 settlements. Cigánd town is the center, the other settlements are: Ricse, Bodroghalom, Dámóc, Karcsa, Karos, Nagyrozvály, Kisrozvály, Lácacséke, Pácin, Révleányvár, Semjén, Tizzacsermely, Tizsakarád, Zemplénagárd. The district consists of small settlements, with an area of 390 km².

Figure 5. Cigánd district in Hungary (dark green)

Source: https://hu.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cig%C3%A1ndi_j%C3%A1r%C3%A1s

The Cigánd district has a **rich history and culture** – most villages in the district were formed in the 10th–14th centuries. Several rivers in the area have posed daily challenges for the locals due to floods; yet, there has been a long history of agricultural activity in the region. In the Middle Ages serfdom was prevalent in agricultural work; after serf emancipation in the 19th century, peasants were allocated small plots of land. However, during the period of socialism, land use was again restricted. Several Agricultural Production Cooperatives (TSZ) were established in the area, where farmers had to submit a portion of their produce (Hajdú, 1997).

The decline of the area can be traced back to the 1970s, when mass emigration began, which has continued ever since. Similar processes took place in several areas in Hungary: villagers began

migrating *en masse* to economic centres during the late communist era, leaving some trapped due to the inability to move. This also meant that the Roma population living in the Roma settlements next to the villages moved into the vacant rural houses (Ladányi, 2010). The process resulted the creation of **numerous rural/Roma slums** in the region. Poorly planned and extensively built low-quality housing units constructed in the 1990s also affected current housing conditions, exacerbating living conditions and pushing down housing prices (BTKT, 2016b). A bridge was built in 1994, and it was a big change for the district – previously, it was hard to navigate transport due to the rivers; the bridge reduced isolation to an extent (BKTK, 2016a).

4.2 Demography

The constant population of the district stood at **16,168 persons** in 2022. According to statistical data, the two vulnerable age groups, children, and the elderly, make up a significant portion of the population (TEIR, 2022). The population decreased by 5 percent between the 2001 and 2022 censuses; during this time period the population of Cigánd district (16,168 persons in 2022) decreased by 15 percent. But this decrease distributes unevenly among the settlements of the district: on the one hand, there are settlements where the population increased between 2001 and 2022 like Karos (6.7 percent) and Semjén (8.3 percent); on the other hand, in other settlements the population decreased by more than 30 percent (Révleányvár, Tiszacsermely, Zemplénagárd, Lácacséke).

If we try to decompose the processes behind this population decrease, we find that the natural change of the population is actually better than on the national level.

On the one hand, there are more newborn as a proportion of the population. While in 2022 there were 9.2 newborn children for every 1,000 persons in the population for the whole country, the same measure was 13.3 for the district on average but varies between 6.7 (Damóc) and 26.1 (Semjén). On the other hand, life expectancy at birth is the lowest in the Northern-Hungarian region: it was 74.1 years in 2022 compared to the national level average of 76 years (maximum was in the capital 78.1). Also, the difference between men and women was the biggest in this region: women tend to live 7.2 years longer on average, on country level this difference was 6.7 years. Moreover, in 2017 the life expectancy of men with low educational attainment (ISCED level 0-2) was 11.2 years lower than men with tertial education (ISCED level 5-8).

Added together these two facts, it follows that on average the population is younger in the district: the proportion of children younger than 10 years old was 5 percentage point higher in the district, the proportion for the age group 10-19 years old the difference is 2.9 percentage point, and for the age group 20-29 the difference is still 3.4 percentage point.

Except for Révleányvár the proportion of young people is higher than the national average (19.6%) in every settlement, but the ration of population younger than 20 years old can be as high as 39.8 percent (Lácacséke) and it is higher than 30 percent in three other settlements as well (Tiszacsermely, Semjén, Kisrozsvány). The ratio of population older than 60 years is below the national average (26.5%) in every settlement, but in Lácacséke, Semjén and Tiszacsermely it is below 15 percent.

Table 4. Distribution of population among age groups (percent)

	Hungary		Cigánd	
	2001	2022	2001	2022
Under 10 years	10.50	9.67	15.03	14.78
10 to 19 years	12.68	9.90	12.82	12.76
20 to 29 years	15.65	11.20	11.91	14.59
30 to 39 years	12.84	12.91	12.07	12.37
40 to 49 years	15.03	16.37	14.08	12.81
50 to 59 years	12.88	13.46	10.68	12.18
60 to 69 years	10.06	12.72	11.02	10.85
70 to 79 years	7.61	9.26	9.77	6.61
80 to 89 years	2.39	3.93	2.33	2.76
90 years and above	0.35	0.59	0.29	0.28

Data source: Hungarian Central Statistical Office (KSH)

Thus, **the main driving force behind the decreasing population is domestic migration**: in 2022 alone, the population decreased by 0.8 percent due to the fact that more people permanently migrated away from these settlements than towards them. As before, there are differences among the settlements: in 2022 the population of Karos increased by 3.6 percent because of domestic migration, on the other end the population of Kisrozsvány decreased by 3.5 (both are small, only have a couple hundred inhabitants, as smaller settlements tend to be more sensitive of some families moving away).

4.3 Economic situation

As previously mentioned, the Cigánd district is located in a **peripheral location**, with few nearby bigger towns. **Agriculture** is one of the main activities in the area, and there is a tradition of small-scale farming and fruit growing in some villages. The region cannot be considered as an independent economic unit, since many residents commute due to the lack of job opportunities. Local municipalities are the largest employers in the region, employing public workers, which is an important means of employment in the area (BTKT, 2016a).

Unemployment is a major problem in the area, with around 1,400 officially registered job seekers in 2022 (source of data: Telr, information system for territorial planning), but a large-scale survey reveals that nearly one in four people are unemployed in reality (NFSZ, 2024). National unemployment rate 4.4%, and it is 9% in Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén county in 2023 (KSH). However, unemployment does not affect all sectors. In addition to many people being unemployed, there is also a **shortage of skilled labour** in highly skilled jobs. One of the most significant challenges facing the economy of this region and the country as a whole is the existence of numerous regions with a multitude of disadvantages. These include a **lack of educational opportunities** for the inhabitants, which in turn results in a dearth of the requisite skills on the labour market.

4.4 Institutional setting

There are **13 primary schools and 11 kindergartens** in the district. The number of kindergarten places is 755, which, based on the previously mentioned population data, indicates a low ratio of places per

capita. In many places, children only start kindergarten at the age of 5, mostly due to a shortage of places. There is just one high school, which is in the district centre. According to interviews and previous research, poor educational opportunities greatly hinder children's mobility. In addition to the lack of institutions and teachers, educational difficulties are exacerbated by the fact that many children struggle with **learning and behavioural problems** due to their disadvantaged backgrounds. In the north-eastern counties of the country, the number of people with only primary school education is higher than the national average, and Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén county has the 2nd highest number of public workers in the country (people with only primary school education is over-represented among public workers in the country).

According to a health survey conducted in 2018, **the health status of residents of the Cigánd district is inadequate**. Regarding subjective health status, 38.4% of respondents reported recurring illnesses, with 4.8 people requiring hospital care (Rusinné et al., 2018). In contrast, there are **no hospital beds per 1,000 people** – which means there are no hospitals in the district (source of data: Telr). The district's health service faces capacity shortages in several villages, and the situation is particularly critical in paediatric care. People often have to travel 18–40 kilometres from several villages to see a doctor (BTKT, 2016a). Thus, basic needs such as medical examination are not accessible in every village, forcing residents to travel to other villages.

As mentioned earlier, the number of commuters who work in other villages is high. In light of this, the underdevelopment of the region's infrastructure is a particularly significant problem. **Public transportation and road networks are very poor**. Public transport is expensive and not well timed or there are no transport connections, and the road network is in a very bad condition; the roads are potholed and fragmented (MRSZ, n.a.). Additionally, the number of cars per 100 inhabitants is half the national average. The underdevelopment of infrastructure exacerbates the isolation of the region and increases the vulnerability of its residents. The greater the distance workers have to travel, the greater the immobility (KSH, n.a.). Without a car, it is practically impossible or very difficult to access everyday necessities and services in the region. Moreover, due to the proximity of rivers, **flood protection** remains an unresolved issue in the village.

Social and child protection benefits play an important role in preventing poverty and supporting disadvantaged families. However, underfunding, low wages and a lack of professionals pose serious challenges in terms of the efficiency of the system, while overloading and the lack of special services further complicate the operation of the social sector.

Several programs (mainly managed by local organisations and nation-wide NGOs) have been aimed at developing the region, since economic and social disadvantages continue to increase:

- The "**Magic Garden Sure Start Children's House**", established as part of the regional Child Guarantee program in Lácacséke, operates with municipal support (during the Child Guarantee Program it was supported via EU funds, but after the end of the funding period the municipality had started to support the institution in order to remain operable). The Sure Start Program's aim is to help children (and their parents) living in poor and/or socially excluded families, by

developing the cognitive and social skills needed to succeed at school and helping parents to develop these skills at home. By this, therefore, children's houses aim to stop the re-emergence of low educational attainment and poverty (Balás et al., 2016).

- The **Hungarian Reformed Church Charity**, within the framework of the "Infinite Opportunity" (an ESF funded program), had initiated developmental work based on a comprehensive, diagnosis-based local presence methodology (settlement-type social work). The project developed solutions in six interventions areas. The first area was the poor condition of the road network and deficiencies in public transportation. As part of the program, a bus service was established in the district, allowing families access to various services. (However, the bus service provided by the charity organization alone is not sufficient to ensure equal access. It would be necessary to coordinate the village bus networks of local governments and the vehicle fleets of social service providers. In addition, further resources are needed to improve the quality of the road network to increase regional accessibility.) Numerous services and training courses were provided in the district as part of the project, which could promote improvements in quality of life and reduce emigration. These include the operating of Presence Points, where local residents can get help with solving their problems, as well as district service roundtables and development forums, which better utilize resources (this method was continued in the succession of the program, the Catching-up Settlement Programme). They provided educational programs for children, community initiatives, and robotics workshops. For adults, the program has given assistance in approaching the labour market and increasing motivation for employment through the Bokréta-Workwear program.
- As part of the "Infinite Opportunity" project, various **knowledge-enhancing training courses** were held for professionals working in the social care system. These included community development, Roma mediator and facilitator training, as well as parenting training sessions to facilitate direct work with families. As a successor of this initiative, the government has launched a nationwide program (Catching-up Settlement Programme, FETE) to support the development of the 300 most disadvantaged municipalities, including several municipalities in Cigánd district, and in the Bodrogköz. They provide comprehensive assistance in rural development and are present in everyday difficulties; many elements of the Infinite Opportunity programme have been continued in the area (especially those targeting small children).

4.5 Local policies and instruments

In Hungary, the local public authority is exercised by local governments at the settlement level, as defined in the Fundamental Law. The Hungarian system of more than 3,000 municipalities is characterised by fragmentation, significant inequalities, limited autonomy, limited powers and responsibilities, limited competence to carry out local public affairs, and limited resources and economic margins (Palné Kovács, 2022,2023). In Hungary, municipalities have been engaged in the preparation of a Settlement Development Plan. This strategic document defines the long-term

development directions and goals of a municipality, as well as the measures needed to achieve them. The objective is to ensure that the development of the settlement is coordinated, sustainable and based on local needs. The plan include:

- The Local Development Concept outlines the general, long-term objectives,
- The Integrated Spatial Development Strategy (ITS) provides a more detailed, medium-term framework for development,
- Finally, action plans specify the specific projects and timetables for their implementation (314/2012. (XI. 8.) Gov. decree).

These elements are mutually reinforcing, collectively constituting the foundation for the municipality's future growth and development. The objective of the documents is to facilitate sustainable development of the municipality, with due consideration of the needs of its inhabitants and the efficient utilisation of available resources. This strategy serves as the foundation for accessing development resources. The preparation of a Settlement Development Plan is a mandatory requirement for cities with county status, larger cities and regional centres, and municipalities involved in EU projects. Other municipalities are not obliged to prepare an Settlement Development Plan, but are encouraged to do so if they wish to access development funds. These documents have not been prepared in all municipalities, thus allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of previous planning documents.

Prior to 2022, the municipalities had developed only the Integrated Spatial Development Strategy (ITS), which aimed to facilitate coordinated long-term development of their economic, social, environmental and infrastructural areas. This document will be subject to review during the forthcoming planning cycle. In the MAP area, the existence of an Integrated Spatial Development Strategy (ITS) varies from one municipality to another, mainly according to the size of the municipality and its stage of development. The town of Cigánd, as the centre of the district, had an ITS (dated 2015) which defined medium-term development objectives and related projects.¹⁴

The following strategic development objectives have been identified:

- To improve the conditions for employment growth. This will be achieved by developing the business environment, encouraging industry relocation, expanding entrepreneurial services, developing a value-added social economy, investing in society, developing local human resources, and helping women into work. The latter will be facilitated by improving the capacity of nursery and kindergarten provision.
- The creation of a service city centre. This will be achieved by strengthening the service functions of the district centre, developing the human services of the city centre, and

¹⁴ <http://www.cigand.hu/dokumentumok.html>

community-oriented urban regeneration. The attractiveness of the city centre will also be improved.

- The creation of a human and service sub-centre will entail improvements to the quality of the healthcare system and the development of sports and leisure infrastructure.
- The creation of attractive residential areas and the improvement of the quality of life of people living in slums are key objectives. This will be achieved by improving the quality of life of people living in slums, improving municipal infrastructure, and improving urban transport.
- The promotion of culture-based spatial development in the Bodrogeköz is a further objective. This will be achieved by revitalising cultural and natural heritage, networking attractions and organising them into tourism products, developing experiences, integrating tourism into the historic Bodrogeköz, and regenerating the Bodrogeköz community.

Furthermore, in accordance with Act CLXXXIX of 2011 on Local Governments in Hungary, municipal governments were obliged to devise and implement an Economic Programme (EP) for each municipality, which delineates the strategic parameters for its operations and economic development. The Economic Programme of the Municipality of Cigánd (covering the period 2019-2024) identifies the development of the social economy as a key project, with the objective of strengthening municipal-owned companies. The Economic Program identifies the following key projects: the development of the Industrial Park, the construction of the Incubation Hall; the development of the Bodrog Intermunicipal Museum and active tourism; the development of the road connecting Cigánd and Sáropatak; and the renovation of the roads. The town's key projects include the construction of rental housing, a resettlement programme, the creation of community space for young people, the development of the social economy – with a focus on strengthening municipal companies – the construction of a residential home for the elderly, and the organisation of secondary education (marketable vocational training) linked to sport.¹⁵

The micro-regional/ district level is of fundamental importance in rural areas (G. Fekete 2013). The current system of districts was established in 2013 as part of the administrative reform programme, with the intention of replicating the structure that had been abolished in 1983. The objective was to diminish the administrative fragmentation that had been occurring since the 1990's. In 2013, the district offices assumed responsibility for a range of functions previously undertaken by the municipalities, including document management, child protection and guardianship, and certain social, environmental and nature protection administrative matters. Furthermore, following the centralisation of public education, the regional bodies were also transferred to the district level, designated as school districts (Fábián-Hoffman, 2016). As statistical territorial units, the districts were thus situated at an intermediate level between the county and the settlement, primarily fulfilling an administrative role.

¹⁵ Cigánd Város Gazdasági Programja 2019-2024, Cigánd, 2020. április 30

The way social services are provided and developed is defined in the Service Planning Concept (Szt. 92§)¹⁶, are drawn up by municipalities, county councils and associations with a population of at least 2 000. The districts are currently not involved in spatial development, although the adoption of an Integrated Spatial Development Strategy (ITS) is compulsory for district centres. In addition to this, district centres may present their own role and development objectives, as well as those of the other municipalities.¹⁷ In the context of the Cigándi district, it is pertinent to draw attention to the existence of the Bodrogközi Multipurpose Micro-regional Partnership. The Bodrogközi Multipurpose Micro-regional Social Service Centre represents an integrated institution. The professional units within the organisational framework perform a range of social and child welfare tasks, as well as the tasks of the Family and Child Welfare Centre throughout the district. These include the provision of social meals, a day club for the elderly, home care, a day club for the disabled, family care and social assistance. Among the professional developments, the 'Bodrog Intermunicipal Integrated Children's Programmes' project, which focuses on children, is worthy of particular mention. This project was implemented in order to provide services in support of three specific objectives. The programme's stated objectives are threefold: to reduce material poverty rates for children and their families, to improve children's educational opportunities and life chances, and to reduce the incidence of extreme forms of child exclusion and segregation and of deviance that undermine life chances. While the programme makes no mention of the role of the social economy, its stated objectives and activities include the development of local job supply and the integration of incubators into the labour market through public and municipal employment.

Furthermore, as part of the Hungarian Reformed Church Aid (MRSZ) project, "INFINITE POSSIBILITIES – COMPLEX DEVELOPMENT OF THE CIGAND DISTRICT", a comprehensive development plan for the district was devised, encompassing proposals for advancement across a range of domains.

- The area's road network is in a poor state of repair, and there are deficiencies in public transport.
- The population is in decline.
- The local economy is characterised by structural unemployment, low educational attainment, a lack of labour market skills, and income poverty.
- There has been an increase in the number of disadvantaged pupils, behavioural problems, and learning difficulties.
- There is a shortage of social workers, and professionals working in the social care system lack the requisite specialised knowledge.

¹⁶ 1993. évi III. törvény a szociális igazgatásról és szociális ellátásokról

¹⁷ After January 1, 2022, the ITS will be replaced by the so-called "settlement development plan", which will be prepared on the basis of a different methodology than the previous one, based on the Government Decree 419/2021 (VII. 15.) on the content, preparation and adoption of settlement plans and on certain specific legal instruments of settlement planning.

The Bodrogeköz EGTC (European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation) is active in the MAP area. The Bodrogeköz EGTC serves to facilitate the joint implementation of cross-border, transnational, or interregional cooperation projects by local governments and other public bodies in Hungary and Slovakia.

Additionally, the Zemplén Landscapes Rural Development Association (ZLRDA) represents a LAG with the objective of facilitating rural development cooperation and the implementation of the local rural development strategy. The association was established as an NGO, comprising representatives from local government, business and civil society, in accordance with EU regulations governing proportional representation. The organisation participates in the European Union's CLLD/LEADER programme, which facilitates the utilisation of EAFRD/CAP resources. In 2008 the association was designated a LEADER Local Action Group, a status which has been maintained continuously since that date. The Local Action Group (LAG) is currently engaged in the preparation of a Local Development Strategy for the period spanning 2023 to 2027. The preliminary version of this strategy is currently in progress. The strategy's primary objectives are as follows:

1. To facilitate the establishment, sustenance and growth of micro-enterprises within rural communities.
2. To develop and implement complex, sustainable tourism and catering programmes based on local cooperation, which showcase the region's natural and other values, endowments, traditions and unique products.
3. To enhance community life, community marketing, infrastructure development of community spaces and the conservation of built and cultural heritage.
4. To implement renewable energy, climate-friendly, water retention and environmental protection solutions at the local level.
5. To promote the development of smart village strategies.

5. Vulnerability and social exclusion in the Cigánd region

5.1 Social exclusion and poverty

In Northern-Hungarian region the share of **people living in severe material and social deprivation** was 31.5 percent in 2015, which was the highest value among the regions; meanwhile the national average was 24.1 percent. As indicators based on the SILC database can only be calculated on regional level due to sample sizes, we are using the decomposition of Tátrai (2022) from the previous section to show the district level estimation for the proportion of people living in severe material deprivation. This indicator was **44 percent** in 2014 in the Cigánd district, which was the 16th worst from the 175 districts at the time. Since 2015 the share of people living with severe material deprivation decreased to 10.4 percent (13.7 percentage point decrease) on national average in 2023, and in the Northern-Hungarian region this share decreased to 21.4 percent (10.1 percentage point decrease), but it is still the highest value among the regions.

In the Northern-Hungarian region 22.4 percent of the population was **at-risk-of poverty** in 2014; that was the second worst value among the regions, meanwhile the national average was 15 percent. From the same estimation (Tátrai 2022) the proportion of relative income poverty was **37 percent** in the district (even higher than for the region), which was the 6th worst in the country at the time. Similarly to the proportion of population with material deprivation, the share of population at-risk-of poverty is also declined since 2015. By 2023 only 12 percent of the national population was at-risk-of poverty, and 15.4 percent in the Northern-Hungarian region, it was still among the highest values in Hungary (after Southern Transdanubia 18.5% and Northern Great Plain 16%).

Both indicators show that the share of population with bad living condition is estimated significantly higher than the regional average, which in itself is the among the worst regions of the country. In the past years both the national and the regional average improved, but without fresh estimation we don't know how the improvements affected the district.

According to the 2022 census the proportion of population with less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (ISCED level 0-2) was 23.8 percentage points higher in Cigánd district than the average of the country. On the other hand, the proportion of population with upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED level 3-4) was 9.2 percentage points lower and the proportion of population with tertiary education (ISCED level 5-8) was 1.5 percentage points lower.

5.2 Labour market

According to the data of the Central Statistics Office, using the census categories (which are not the same as the ILO definitions), in 2022 on average 57.5 percent of the population above 15 years was employed on the country level, 2.9 percent was unemployed, 27.6 percent was economically inactive persons receiving benefits and 12.1 percent was dependent persons. The distribution of population in Cigánd district in 2022 was 49 percent employed (8.5 percentage point lower), 6.6 percent

unemployed (3.7 percentage point higher) and 31.9 percent (4.3 percentage point higher) inactive persons receiving benefits. This means that on average, the population of the district is less employed, with a **higher share of unemployed and inactive persons**.

This goes along with the fact that **public employment is more important** in the district than on national level. In the district the proportion of population between 15 of 64 years employed in a public work scheme is 11.3 percent, the same ratio 1.1 percent on national level.

Interviews have reinforced that the main economic profile of the district is agricultural with a very low level of services and industry. The **firm size in agriculture is dominantly small, mainly small scale businesses and individual farmers**.

5.3 Disadvantaged groups

The biggest ethnic minority in Hungary are the **Gipsies/Romas**; however, we only have estimations for their numbers. László Hablicsek in 2007 forecasted the number of Romanies to be 733–814 thousand by 2021 (Hablicsek, 2007). The TÁRKI 2012 Household Monitor survey reported an estimation of 620,000 to 680,000 people (Bernát, 2012).

In the 2022 census only 209,909 people declared themselves to be part of the Roma community. As this data is based on self-declaration, it can be biased (e.g. people assume repercussions for declaring themselves Gipsy) in the census database; but there is no reason to assume that these biases are different in the Cigánd district than anywhere else in the country. The proportion of self-declared Gipsies was 2.2 percent in the whole country, and at the same time it was **11.6 percent** in the district. Among the settlements in the region, the self-declared proportion of Roma people spreads between 0 and 65 percent, usually with a higher proportion in the smaller settlements (below 400 inhabitants).

Infant mortality was more than four times higher in the district (14.3 per 1,000 live birth) than the national average (3.3 per 1,000 live birth) in 2021.

The proportion of disadvantaged children in kindergartens was 18.1 percent in the district and only 4.6 percent on national average; similarly, in primary schools the ratio of disadvantaged kids was 16.8 percent in the district and 5.3 percent on national level.¹⁸ The proportion of the population younger than 20 years old receiving regular child protection benefit was 58.5 percent in the district and 12 percent on national average. This data shows (and the interviews have reinforced) that child poverty is a serious problem in the district.

5.4 Access to services

There are only **55 nursery/daycare places available** in the district (in three settlements), which means 12.3 children below 3 years per place; meanwhile the national average is 5.1 young children per place

¹⁸ Before the change in the definition of disadvantaged children back in 2013, both ratios were higher on district and national level, but the difference between the district and national level was the same (the district value was triple of the national value back then as well).

(the national average is that 20 percent of young children have a place; in the district this is only 8 percent).

There are 13 primary schools in the district, and the district's schools on average are half the size than the national average (108 pupils in the district, 200 pupils on national level), but the pupil-teacher ratio is the same as the national average. **There is no secondary school in the district**, only in neighbouring districts (Sárospatak, Sátoraljaújhely, Kisvárda), so every student has to take the bus to go to school which can take hours.

There is **no hospital** in the district, only a clinic with specialists. There are only seven general and family practitioners in the district, on average with little more than 1,660 adult inhabitants per doctor, which is lower than the national average.

Table 4. Socioeconomical indicators of the district, 2015 – 2022

Cigánd district	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Population (persons)	17,046	16,987	16,871	16,753	16,668	16,496	1,6255	16,168
Percentage of the permanent population aged 0-14 (%)	19.44	19.5	19.31	19.82	20.14	20.36	20.79	21.06
Percentage of the permanent population aged 65-x (%)	14.09	14.03	14.1	13.99	13.98	14.23	14.12	14
Natural increase, decrease (‰)	0	0.94	-0.63	1.92	1.81	-1.11	-6.38	-1.15
Internal migration balance, per thousand inhabitants (‰)	-10.81	-11.01	-9.44	-13.67	-14.77	-13.97	-17.81	-16.25
0-17-year-olds in the permanent population (persons)	4,060	4,060	4,022	4,033	4,038	3,995	4,032	4,034
Number of disadvantaged and severely disadvantaged children and children reaching majority (persons)	2,586	2,780	2,619	2,446	2,383	2,335	2,452	2,185
Children at risk (2016 onwards methodology) (persons)	-	-	-	-	187	262	146	216
Disadvantaged preschool children (%)	70.2	68.5	73.22	70.57	30.1	23.5	28.8	18.14
Disadvantaged primary school pupils (%)	75.28	74.98	75.79	69.69	26.09	20.32	22.28	16.81
Average monthly number of persons receiving regular child protection benefits (persons)	-	-	2,825	2,666	2,576	2,465	2,577	2,381

Average monthly number of persons in receipt of regular child protection support, per 100 0-18-year-olds (persons)	-	-	68.29	64.09	61.79	59.85	62.29	57.61
Total registered jobseekers (persons)	1,344	1,083	1,137	1,251	1,293	1,267	1,349	1,447
Registered jobseekers per 100 persons aged 15-64 (persons)	9.79	7.92	8.35	9.31	9.71	9.64	10.48	11.34
Percentage of registered jobseekers with 8 or less years of primary education (%)	62.35	60.94	63.85	65.55	62.03	60.46	64.05	63.44
Average monthly number of persons in receipt of employment substitution benefit (persons)	-	-	569	563	679	623	616	630
Participants in public employment (annual average of monthly data) (persons)	2,174	2,208	1,796	1,491	1,358	1,314	1,237	1,128
Percentage of jobseekers registered for more than 180 days (%)	45.16	42.01	43.98	50.28	56.07	54.46	61.68	64.41
Income tax payers per 100 inhabitants (persons)	42.54	48.64	48.31	49.14	48.03	47.34	47.62	47.2
Percentage of income tax payers in income bracket below HUF 1 million (~ EUR 2,500) per year (%)	50.57	53.68	48.6	45.05	36	43.77	36.41	31.01
Persons receiving food benefits (persons)	732	742	755	731	709	761	761	804

Source: Telr (information system for territorial planning)

6. Assets and potentials in the region

This area has a (yet untapped) **touristic potential**, according to our inquiries. The natural environment offers a panoramic view, freshwater, mountainous areas which are hilly enough to bike on them – and a living connection to the Slovakian part of the Bodrogköz area. Cycling tourism is envisioned to be a breakthrough activity for the area – however, there are very few facilities available at this point to serve the needs of (potential) tourists.

According to some interviews, another main asset of the region is – even though there are multiple problems people and institutions face – that there is **proactivity**, and there is a **need for joint reflection** in stakeholders. There is cooperation among the local mayors, and they have a **regional vision** about development, which is considered a potential on which new ideas can be built upon.

“So that kind of thinking, that they can think in terms of improvements, and they are interested in how it can be better, more efficient. I think that's an absolute potential [...] So we don't really see that kind of complex approach elsewhere, that they look at themselves, their own development in that way. Here too, of course, there are developments without context, but perhaps in this region I have seen that there is a desire for coordination between mayors...” (NGO worker)

There is **cooperation between different stakeholders**; the formal networks and cooperation which were created in EU-funded projects (especially in Child Guarantee projects) are meaningful and able to carry out their tasks. Interviewees mentioned that while lack of expertise is a severe issue in the region, there are some professionals who remained (in social services, but also in implementation and administration of projects), and who can be brought into networks and projects. This is an important asset in knowledge transfer.

It is important to note that these stakeholders are mostly institutional, political or church-related actors; **organised civil society, as such, is very limited in the area**. The existing civil organisations, according to interviewees and some of the literature, are either ‘quasi-civil’ organisations, which were mostly created for the purpose of being able to apply for funds for NGOs; or cultural associations for preserving traditions, and sports associations. The reason behind this might be twofold (BTKT, 2016b): the scarcity of intellectuals, on the one hand, since emigration hit this groups first; those who left had not reattached the cultural and social capital that they acquire and build up when they move away. On the other hand, there might be some connection with the fact that only selected few are able to represent their interest actively and successfully, which opposes the formulation of a strong civil sector.

This also means that the existing networks and cooperation usually do not involve CSO partners (or they only do if one counts church charity organisations there). Local needs and interest are usually represented by (political or other) institutional actors.

While there are some social economy organisations in the district, the concept is usually foreign to most people. ‘True’ social enterprises, therefore, are rare – and local attitudes vary: one of the

interviewees has mentioned that due to historical reasons, people are more likely to reject 'social cooperatives', only because of their name.

In the Cigánd district, there are 66 non-profit organisations registered with the Statistical Office (KSH), which represents a ratio of 451 organisation per 100,000 inhabitants. This is significantly lower than the national average of 636 organisations per 100,000 inhabitants. Of the total number of non-profit organisations, 56 can be categorised as traditional NGOs, which include foundations and associations. The region is among the most disadvantaged in Hungary. The majority of registered NGOs in the region are situated in town areas. It should be noted that there are numerous other non-registered citizen groups in the municipalities whose activities are primarily focused on culture and education. One of the most prominent umbrella organizations in the region is the Sárospatak and Zemplén Regional Association of Disabled People. The most significant organisations, in terms of both membership numbers and overall activity, are primarily engaged in the domains of sport, education and leisure. In order to identify social enterprises. We conducted an analysis of the organisations' balance sheets, focusing on those with a notable level of business income and active engagement. Of the organisations examined, 14 met this criterion, although there are also some that are not active or have been established with a specific project purpose. The majority of these organisations are social cooperatives linked to municipalities and public work programs.

In the last EU budget period, there was a kind of **abundance of development projects in this area** (at least partially due to the local mayors' activities); and as it was mentioned before, long-term social projects (FETE for example) are also active in the district. According to some interviews, however, it looks like the developments had not had the desired effect (or not yet).

7. Conclusions and potential focus of MAP

The Cigánd district, containing 15 settlements is located in Hungary, in the North Great Plain region, in Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén country. It is situated in an extremely isolated location, directly next to the Slovakian border; and is one of the most disadvantaged areas in the country. The decline of the area can be traced back to the 1970s, when mass emigration began, which has continued ever since; combined with the creation of numerous rural/Roma slums in the region.

According to statistical data, **children** make up a significant portion of the local population. Migration balance is negative in the region; even though many children are being born each year, moving away is greater. The population is 11.6% of **Roma** origin, counted based on self-declaration – local estimates suggest 30%.

Unemployment is a major problem in the area (the unemployment rate of the county is double the national average); however, it does not affect all sectors: in addition to many people being unemployed, there is also a shortage of skilled labour in highly skilled jobs.

Thus, the region is struggling with a **shrinking population**, and **low educational attainment** (a lot of poor children with high chances of early school leaving), which – with a circular reasoning – leads to low employability and higher rates of poverty, which leads to a low demand for goods and services combined, which, combined with bad infrastructure, results in few jobs.

The managers of the local MAP have to confront the hindrances of the **weak civil sector** in the area; however, the **proactivity of political and institutional actors** can help them, and with good facilitating can represent the local needs. There are multiple helping factors and conditions for the MAP:

- there is a strong project application and organisational potential in the Cigánd district – they can build on a strategy to build several projects connected to each other,
- a situation assessment has already been carried out to prepare a strategy – so there is existing knowledge,
- there is local knowledge of the institutional landscape, and established infrastructure of the aid organisations in the field,
- churches have recently become more active in the area, which might help facilitating discourse,
- the already existing experience of the team in social enterprises – they have helped to organise them before.

The MAP in Bodrogek, according to our interviewees, could contribute to the development in the area in the following:

- maintaining dialogue, facilitating cooperation,
- disseminating new techniques,
- finding experts.

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